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Bias in public datasets

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1 Introduction

The recent developments and advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems enable the possibility to use them in different domains, including those where AI is responsible for making decisions that can impact one's life. In these kind of domains, bias can occur in different forms such as racial, gender, ethnicity or social-economic. Such biases can change the outcomes of machine learning models, leading for example to wrongly categorized data in the case of a classification task. The content of the training data or the way the training data is collected can lead to bias in any machine learning model trained on it.

Therefore, the aim of this project is to analyze whether public datasets containing sensitive attributes such as gender, age or race, are biased in regard to this attributes and if so, what could be the reasons that lead to such results. To evaluate the fairness in machine learning models trained on various datasets, an open audit toolkit called Aequitas is used. All the datasets analyzed for this project are publicly available on OpenML website and are distributed under the CC-BY license [1].

2 Related Work

2.1 State of the Art

Nowadays, machine learning algorithms are part of our society and they can help people make various decisions: what music to listen to, what to buy, or what movie to watch. On top of that, machine learning algorithms have started to be used in domains where they make more important decisions such as hiring decisions, in facial recognition, for bank loans, or for various medical tasks. Although one might think that such algorithms should make more precise and fair decisions, in reality machine learning algorithms and their outputs can be influenced by bias.

2.1.1 Related work

Given the increased use of machine learning algorithms in various domains, numerous analyses have been undertaken to verify the fairness of their predictions. Researchers have been investigating models that are employed in domains where biased predictions can affect individuals' lives. Such example is the tool used for making decisions in children maltreatment hotline screenings, called Allegheny Family Screening Tool (AFST). This tool was developed to help social workers decide whether a maltreatment complaint is worth investigating further (screened-in) or not (screened-out). To decide on that, the model assigned a score to 1 to 20 for each complaint, where 20 meant that a child should be replaced in a new home. In [2] it was found that black children with score 20 had a higher chance to result in placement rather than white children with the same score. Another example is the Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS) tool which was used in the United States to analyze the risk of a convicted person to perform another crime in the future. Based on this tool, judges decided whether a person should be released earlier from prison or not. In the analysis of this software [3] it was discovered that for black people the false positive rates are much higher than for white people. For instance, the software assigned a higher risk score to a young woman who was accused of misdemeanors than to a white man who committed armed robberies. Unfairness was also found in facial recognition software, where the algorithm performed better for white male faces [4].

2.1.2 Bias sources

In machine learning models, bias can occur in different phases of the AI life cycle such as the collection of training data or the model design. This will lead to obtaining unfair and biased results. In [5], the authors provide an in depth description of all types of bias that can influence machine learning models. They categorize bias definitions into three main categories: data to algorithm, algorithm to user and user to data. Below a brief summary of these three categories will be explained:

- **Data to algorithm:** If the algorithm is trained on a biased data, then the relationships between input data and targets that it discovers will be biased as well. This will eventually lead to biased predictions when it attempts to generalize to new data. This type of bias can result from the way the data was chosen or sampled and can be caused by:
 - Not having enough diversity in the data: Having insufficiently represented subgroups in a dataset can make the model perform worse on these subgroups since it does not learn from these samples as much as those from other groups during training. This means that the algorithm has less information about the under represented groups.
 - Omitting important attributes: Leaving out one or more important attributes can exclude significant information that the model would base its prediction off of. Therefore the exclusion of these attributes can change the prediction results and can negatively affect the model's performance.
 - Having attributes that are interpreted to have a relationship with the target attribute that they do not actually encapsulate. These attributes usually act as stand-ins for concepts that cannot be directly quantified (proxy attributes [6]).
- **Algorithm to user:** Bias in machine learning algorithms will affect their output which will also lead to a biased user experience. This type of bias is not necessarily connected to the input data, but can be caused during the algorithm design, optimization, regularization and whenever the developers evaluate the model's performance.
- **User to data:** In many cases, the datasets on which the machine learning models are trained on, are based on data generated by users (polls, web searches, reviews, etc). The bias in the user will reflect in the choices they make and therefore the data they create.

2.1.3 Methods for mitigating bias

There are many ways and methods to try reduce the bias in machine learning models. In [5] the authors grouped them into three categories:

- **Pre-processing:** Transforms the data before training to avoid or reduce the existing bias. This can include re-sampling or re-weighting the data.
- **In-processing:** Modifies the existing machine learning algorithms in such way that the bias is minimized. There are numerous methods that try to improve the fairness in machine learning models. For instance, there is some existing work that tries to improve machine learning algorithms such as modifying Naive Bayes Classifier [7], creating a fair regression algorithm [8] or a fair PCA model [9].
- **Post-processing:** Uses data that was not used for training to analyze the bias.

2.1.4 Tools for investigating fairness in machine learning models

Analyzing and investigating unfairness and bias in the outputs of machine learning models can be a difficult task because it requires inspecting the output and computing various statistical metrics. To ease this task, different toolkits or libraries that can detect bias have been developed in the last years, such as FairML [10], Fairlearn [11], AIFairness360 [12] or Aequitas which was used for this project.

3 Methods

3.1 Aequitas

As previously mentioned, Aequitas¹ toolkit was used for this project. Developed by the Center for Data Science and Public Policy at University of Chicago, this toolkit is an open source bias audit that can be used to analyze whether the predictions made by a machine learning model are biased or not. The tool can be accessed via the following implementations:

- Python library
- Command Line Tool
- WebApp

The developers of Aequitas wanted to make this toolkit accessible not only for machine learning developers but also for analysts and policymakers, therefore the command line tool and the web audit tool do not require any programming skills. The only requirement to run these two is to have a dataset that already contains predictions made by a machine learning model [13]. For this project, only the Python library was used, as it is simple to integrate it with existing code.

3.1.1 Input data

In order to obtain the bias report in any case, the input data must be standardized according to the requirements found on the Aequitas website [14]. The input data must contain two binary columns: a column called "score" for predictions and a column called "label_value" for the true label values. Since they are required to be binary, the Aequitas tool can be only used for binary class classifications or for linear regression problems that can be afterwards converted into a binary classification using a threshold value. Besides these two columns, the sensitive columns must be added as well. The sensitive columns are those that the user wants to audit for bias, for instance sex, age, race, income, education, etc. They can be either

¹<http://aequitas.dssg.io/>

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categorical or numerical and the user is free to choose which attributes are considered sensitive. Other attributes that are not considered sensitive do not need to be added to the input data.

3.1.2 Output data

After having the table containing the input data, the tool can be used to obtain the output reports with the fairness and bias metrics. The reports can include: group metrics, bias report, disparity metrics or fairness. To generate the output, the toolkit expects a reference group for each attribute defined as sensitive. The reference group is defined by user and can be either the group with the most representation in a category or it can be a group that is believed to be more preferred than the others.

3.2 Measuring Bias and Fairness with Aequitas

3.2.1 Statistical metrics

Statistical metrics can be derived from the confusion matrix which is a table commonly used in machine learning literature to describe and analyze the performance of a classifier. To assess fairness, these metrics are used to quantify the disparities and imbalances between different groups. For a binary classification task, the confusion matrix contains four elements:

- **True positive (TP):** cases that belong to the positive class and are predicted positive.
- **True negative (TN):** cases that belong to the negative class and are predicted negative.
- **False positive (FP):** cases that belong to the negative class but are predicted positive.
- **False negative (FN):** cases that belong to the positive class but are predicted negative.

The table 3.1 displays the confusion matrix for binary classification tasks.

3.2 Measuring Bias and Fairness with Aequitas

	Actual positive	Actual negative
Predicted positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
Predicted negative	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

Table 3.1: Confusion Matrix

Using these four definitions, different statistical metrics can be derived. The following metrics are the ones used in the Aequitas tool to make decisions regarding the bias of an input dataset [15]:

1. **Predictive positive value (Precision)**: represents the probability of cases predicted positive to actually belong to the predicted positive class.

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} = P(Y = 1|\hat{Y} = 1)$$

2. **Predictive negative value**: represents the probability of cases predicted negative to actually belong to the predicted negative class.

$$NPV = \frac{TN}{TN+FN} = P(Y = 0|\hat{Y} = 0)$$

3. **Predicted Prevalance**: represents the fraction of entities from a group for which the true outcome was positive.

$$Prev_g = LP_g/|g| = P(Y = 1|A = a_i)$$

4. **Predicted Positive Rate**: represents the fraction of a group which were predicted as positive.

$$PPR_g = PP_g/K = P(a = a_i|\hat{Y} = 1)$$

5. **False Discovery Rate**: represents the fraction of negative cases that were predicted positive out of all positive predicted cases.

$$FDR = \frac{FP}{FP+TP} = P(Y = 0|\hat{Y} = 1)$$

6. **False Omission Rate**: represents the fraction of positive cases that were predicted negative out of all negative predicted cases.

$$FOR = \frac{FN}{FN+TN} = P(Y = 1|\hat{Y} = 0)$$

7. **True Positive Value (Sensitivity/Recall)**: represents the probability of cases predicted positive to actually belong to the actual positive class.

$$TPV = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} = P(Y = 1|\hat{Y} = 1)$$

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8. **False Positive Rate:** represents the fraction of cases predicted incorrectly positive out of all negative actual cases.

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP+TN} = P(Y = 0|\hat{Y} = 1)$$

9. **False Negative Rate:** represents the fraction of cases predicted incorrectly negative out of all positive actual cases.

$$FNR = \frac{FN}{FN+TP} = P(Y = 1|\hat{Y} = 0)$$

10. **True Negative Rate:** represents the probability of cases predicted negative to actually belong to the actual negative class.

$$TNR = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} = P(Y = 0|\hat{Y} = 0)$$

Aequitas calculates these metrics for each subgroup from a sensitive attribute and provides a table with the results.

3.3 Definitions of fairness

There are multiple definitions of fairness since it is very difficult to define only one single definition. Describing the fairness can vary based on the situation, preferences, culture, etc. In Aequitas, the authors defined a fairness criteria that decides if a group meets the parity. This fairness criteria is defined as follows:

$$(1 - \tau) \leq \frac{\text{statistical metric group}_i}{\text{statistical metric group}_{\text{ref}}} \leq \frac{1}{1 - \tau} \quad (3.1)$$

This criteria is used for all statistical metrics (FPR, FNR, etc) and it calculates the parity for each group category. By default, $\tau = 20\%$ meaning that any parity that is between 0.8 and 1.25 is considered fair [16]. The parity for the reference (protected) group will always be equal to 1. Using this criteria, the toolkit will then compute the following fairnesses and parities [15]:

1. **Statistical Parity:** all groups (both protected and unprotected) should have similar probability of being assigned to the positive class.
2. **Impact parity:** all groups should have similar Prev.
3. **Predictive parity/Precision:** both protected and unprotected groups should have the similar PPV, meaning that all groups should have the same probability to belong to the positive class if they have a positive predicted value.

3.3 Definitions of fairness

4. **Negative predictive value parity:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar NPV, meaning that all groups should have similar probability to belong to the negative class if they have a negative predicted value.
5. **Equalized odds/Disparate mistreatment:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar TPR and FPR, meaning that the probability of a subject from the positive class to be assigned to a positive class and the probability of a subject from the negative class to be assigned incorrectly to the positive class should be the same for both the protected and unprotected groups.
6. **True positive error rate balance:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar TPR.
7. **True negative error rate balance:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar TNR.
8. **False positive error rate balance:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar FPR.
9. **False negative error rate balance/Predictive equal:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar FNR.
10. **False omission error rate balance/Predictive equal:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar FOR.
11. **False discovery error rate balance/Predictive equal:** both protected and unprotected groups should have similar FDR.
12. **Type I parity:** if there is fairness in FPR parity and also FDR parity.
13. **Type II parity:** if there is fairness in FOR parity and also FNR parity.
14. **Unsupervised Fairness:** if there is fairness in Statistical parity and also Impact parity.
15. **Supervised Fairness:** if there is fairness in Type I parity and also Type II parity.
16. **Overall Fairness:** if for all categories from all groups the results are fair.

3.3.1 Fairness Tree

Since Aequitas provides many statistical metrics, the developers together with policymakers created a 'Fairness Tree' (Figure 3.1) that can help users understand better the metrics and check which metrics are more important for their analysis, depending on the task. Hence, if the task results could hurt the individuals (the interventions are punitive), the user should focus more on the FDR and FPR parities, while if the results could help individuals (the results are assistive), the user should pay more attention to the FOR and FNR parities.

Figure 3.1: Fairness tree. [13]

4 Approach

4.1 Data

All the datasets analyzed for this project were downloaded from the OpenML website. OpenML provides thousands of machine learning datasets that can be easily accessed by anyone. Usually, the datasets come with a short description of the content, the source of the dataset, the type of data (numerical or categorical) and most of the time, the target attribute. All datasets on this website contain a unique id.

4.1.1 Categorization of data

In order to filter through all the datasets existing on the website, only the datasets that contained a set of sensitive attributes were chosen. The sensitive attributes were defined in accordance with the Equality Act from 2010 [17] that protects people from being discriminated against the following characteristics: age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy and maternity, race, religion or belief, sex, and sexual orientation. Not all of these characteristics were found in the public datasets. The datasets chosen were also restricted to have always gender or sex as attribute and at least one more sensitive attribute from the list above. Furthermore, all the datasets that had no helpful description or too many missing values in the sensitive attributes were discarded. On top of that, the datasets for which the target attribute could not be converted into a binary class prediction problem were also not considered, since Aequitas can only be used for binary classification problems. After all these restrictions, around 40 datasets were selected. The datasets were then categorized into 5 main topics depending on the classification task description: education, job or income, lifestyle, health, banking or finance.

4.2 Pre-processing of data

Before training machine learning models on the datasets, each of them had to be pre-processed beforehand. Some of the pre-processing steps included:

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- Handling missing values: In cases where the dataset was sufficiently large and included rows with NaNs or null values, particularly in sensitive attributes, the corresponding rows were removed. Columns with non sensitive attributes having too many missing values (more than 50%) were either removed from the dataset or the missing values were imputed: for categorical data the most common value of the column was used and for numerical data the average value of the column was used. Datasets with sensitive columns containing too many missing values were not considered for the analysis.
- Continuous target columns: the target columns that were continuous (used for linear regression tasks) were converted to binary columns due to the limitations of the Aequitas tool. To convert the target column, the median value was used to divide the column into two parts.
- Columns cleaning: columns that were not important for the training (ex: names, ids, etc) were removed from the dataset.
- Sensitive attributes with many categories: if a sensitive column had too many categories from which some were low represented, then the low represented ones were combined into a single category. This was done in order to assure that Aequitas tool can be used also for categories that do not have a high representation in the dataset.

4.3 Data training

Aequitas does not offer a classification tool for the datasets, therefore the classification tasks were done using Python and machine learning libraries: Catboost¹, RandomForrest², scikit-learn³, LogisticRegression⁴. For this project different machine learning algorithms were used to train on the data, depending on the classification task and dataset structure.

The Catboost machine learning algorithm was used most often for this project. This is an algorithm for gradient boosting on decision trees, which can be used for binary or multi-class classifications, as well as for regression tasks. This algorithm builds successive decision trees during training that aim to minimize their error.

¹<https://catboost.ai/>

²<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier.html>

³<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

⁴https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.linear_model.LogisticRegression.html

One advantage of this algorithm is that it can encode categorical features automatically meaning the user does not have to do it manually which reduces the time necessary for pre-processing. Because of this, the user only has to define the categorical features in the training step [18]. This property was helpful because many of the selected datasets contained such features. If Catboost performed poorly on some datasets, then the categorical data was converted to numerical and Random Forest algorithm was used as a comparison.

For the datasets with little or no categorical data, Random Forest algorithm was also used and its results were compared to the ones from Catboost. This algorithm uses also decision trees that are individually trained on smaller sets of the dataset. In some cases, if the classification task was an easy one and the dataset was not too large, logistic regression algorithm was also used.

For training, the data was split into training data, test data and validation data. The model's performance was evaluated using the test data. Some datasets contained an unequal distribution of observations (such as a strong class imbalance) which can lead to bias and bad prediction performances. Normally, in this case pre-processing steps can be applied to mitigate the effect, such as down sampling the most dominant class. Since the goal of this project was to investigate bias in public datasets, it was desired to keep the datasets as much as possible in the original form. This is why only a few changes were done for the training process. However, to avoid too much bias in the prediction results or over-fitting, weight balancing for target classes was used.

4.4 Analysis of results

The test set for each training model was used for running Aequitas. To match the requirements for the toolkit, a new dataset was created containing the following: the test set, the predicted values ("*score*" column) and the true values ("*label_value*" column). Then, the sensitive attributes were defined and the statistical metrics were computed using the methods provided by the toolkit. The statistical metrics were calculated for each category of each sensitive attribute defined. Using these metrics, the disparities for each group could be determined using the fairness criteria defined by the toolkit, for which the value of τ from 3.1 was kept at the default value of 20%.

4.5 Selected datasets

Around 20 datasets were investigated using Aequitas. From all of them, the following showed interesting results:

- **Health category:** Autism prediction (OpenML ID = 42878). This dataset is a collection of recordings from autism screenings performed on adults. Such datasets could be used in detecting earlier if a person suffers from Autistic Spectrum Disorder (ASD). The dataset contains around 705 recordings and the classification task was to predict whether an adult suffers or not from ASD, based on a set of attributes. The following attributes were chosen as sensitive: age, gender and ethnicity.
- **Jobs and income category:** Adult dataset (OpenML ID = 45068). This dataset contains information about working adults such as their occupation, number of hours worked, education but also more personal information such as marital status, race or native country. The data contains around 48,800 entries and the classification task was to predict if an adult earns more than 50,000 dollars per year or if not. The dataset contained as sensitive attributes the following: age, race, sex and marital status.

In addition to this dataset, another income related dataset (OpenML ID = 43141) was analyzed, but in this case the dataset contained over 19 million entries and the target attribute (yearly salary) was initially a continuous one. The target column was divided into two classes by the median value of all the salaries ($\approx 40,000$ dollars). The reason why this dataset was analyzed although the task above is the same, was to investigate how similar tasks are influenced by the size of the data, but also to analyze if a balanced target class can lead to less bias in the results. The sensitive attributes were the same as in the smaller dataset: age, race, sex and marital status.

- **Education category:** Law school admission (OpenML ID = 43904). The target for this dataset is to predict if a person passed the law bar exam or not. The dataset contains around 20,000 entries and the chosen sensitive attributes were: age, race and gender.

The results from these datasets will be discussed in more details in the next chapter.

5 Results and discussion

This chapter presents evaluation results using the Aequitas toolkit, as well as an interpretation of the results.

5.1 Health: autism prediction

- **Analysis and results:** When looking at the category distribution in the original dataset, within every sensitive attribute, it can be noticed that the 'gender' column is fairly distributed (47.9% women and 52.1% men) as seen in 5.1, but the ethnicity columns is dominated by 'White-European' category which can be seen in 5.2. The ethnicity category 'Others' contains all ethnicities that were lowly represented in the dataset.

Figure 5.1: Gender distribution with respect to the true label

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Figure 5.2: Ethnicity distribution with respect to the true label

The data was split into train, test and validation data, where the test data represented 25% of the data and the validation set represented 25% of the train data. Catboost algorithm and Random Forest were used, but the results from Catboost were used for analysis since it performed better. The test data contained about 180 entries, which meant that some categories were insufficiently represented. The reference groups were defined as follow and they represent the most represented group for each category:

- 'gender' : 'male'
- 'ethnicity' : 'White-European'
- 'age' : 'Less than 30'. The age column was initially a continuous one, but it was then divided into two categories using the median value: 'Less than 30' and 'More than 30'. This is an important step when considering age as a sensitive column because Aequitas otherwise calculates the metrics for each age separately, which would not be helpful when analysing the results.

For this prediction task, the 'Fairness Tree' can be used as a guideline for the metrics. Since this dataset could be used to detect ASD earlier, the results are considered assistive, thus in this case more attention is paid to Type II parity, meaning FNR and FOR parity.

Figure 5.3 displays the disparities for FNR and FOR, where the green colour means that the result is fair, while red means that the result is not fair. The fairness criteria was kept to the default value of 20%, meaning that any value for the fairness criteria smaller than 0.8 and bigger than 1.25 will be considered unfair. Looking at the figures we can observe that:

5.1 Health: autism prediction

- For women, both FOR and FNR are smaller than for men, leading to a small value in the disparity report. Similar results can be seen for age category 'Less than 30', where again FOR and FNR are smaller than the reference group.
- FOR disparities for ethnicities are 2x and around 4x higher than for the reference group 'White-European' (for which the disparity is 1), while for FNR the disparities are even higher, highest being the one for 'Middle Eastern' which is around 24. Such high value was caused by the fact that the FNR value for 'Middle Eastern' was ≈ 0.67 while for 'White-European', the value of FNR was very small ≈ 0.03 . A high FOR disparity means that for the selected group the FOR probability is higher than the one of the reference group. This implies that for a person belonging to the 'Middle Eastern' category and suffering from ASD, the chances to be incorrectly diagnosed are much higher than for the other ethnicities.

Figure 5.3: FNR and FOR disparities

Figure 5.4 represents the group fairness, which shows if all groups have similar probability of being assigned to the positive class. It can be observed that besides 'age', all attributes have unfair results. While for 'gender' the differ-

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ence is minimal, for 'ethnicity' the differences are much higher: from the positive predicted values, only 2%, are 'Middle Eastern', 4% are 'Asian' and 20% are 'Other'.

Figure 5.4: Group fairness

- **Conclusion:** one of the reasons why the results are unfair for the sensitive attributes can be the representation of the categories in the original dataset. For 'ethnicity', only 14% are 'Middle Eastern', 17% are 'Asian', 22% are 'Other' and the rest belongs to the 'White-European' category. Another reason can be the disproportion of observations in the target column: only 27% of the entries in the dataset were diagnosed with ASD. Also, the dataset itself contains few recordings (around 700) for the problem that is addressing: determining if an adult suffers from ADS or not.

5.2 Income: yearly salary prediction (1)

- **Results and analysis:** Even though the dataset has almost 49,000 entries, there are imbalances in the data, for instance for the 'race' column, where 87.2% of the entries belong to the 'White' category, while only 8.6% belong to the 'Black' category and the rest belong to the 'Other' category. Moreover, when it comes to the 'Sex' attribute, the percentage of 'Female' earning more than 50k is significantly smaller as shown in figure 5.5

5.2 Income: yearly salary prediction (1)

Figure 5.5: Yearly salary in respect to sex

The data was splitted again into train, test (20% of the data) and validation data (25% of the train data). In this case, Catboost performed again the best. For the Aequitas analysis the following groups were defined as reference:

- 'sex' : Male.
- 'age' : 'Between 30 and 40'. As before, this column was transformed into three categories: 'Less than 30', 'Between 30 and 40' and 'More than 40'.
- 'marital status' : Married.
- 'race' : White.

For this task, the most interesting results were for FNR disparities. Figure 5.6 shows the disparities for each sensitive attribute:

- The FNR parity fails for most categories.
- The squares of the plots are sized accordingly to the size of the category. Therefore the imbalance in some attributes, for instance between 'Male' and 'Female' or between 'White' and the other two categories can be easily noticed.
- For adults that are not married, the chances that the algorithm will predict that they do not earn more than 50k, even though they do, it is much higher than for married people.
- If a category has statistical significance, then the toolkit adds an asterisks (*) to the category. In the disparities figure it can be observed

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that many of the categories that were actually unfair have a statistical significance. The statistical significance value is set by default to 0.05, and if the significance of an attribute is lower than this value, then the attribute is considered significant. The more asterisks it has, the more significant it is (limit is three asterisks).

Figure 5.6: FNR disparities

Looking at the group fairness figure 5.7 it can be observed that only 8% of adults that are not married were correctly predicted as earning more than 50k. The same is for the 'race' attribute where again the 'Black' and 'Other' categories represent only 8% of those that earn more than 50k. Also, only 13% of 'Female' are assigned to be earning more than 50k.

5.3 Income: yearly salary prediction dataset (2)

Figure 5.7: Group fairness

- **Conclusion:** Even though the dataset contains a large number of entries, the data is imbalanced since it contains disproportions in the categories as it was seen in the sections above. Hence the results were expected to show unfairness. For instance, since only 15% of women were earning more than 50k, it is much harder for a machine learning algorithm to correctly assign all those who actually earn more than 50k to the correct class.

5.3 Income: yearly salary prediction dataset (2)

- **Results and analysis:** The dataset already had all the columns converted to numerical on the OpenML website and no detailed description was added about what each category represents in a column. As mentioned in the previous chapter, the target column (income) was a continuous column which was converted to a binary one using the median value as a threshold. Regarding the 'sex' column with respect to the income, the data is more balanced compared to the dataset from the previous section. In the category below the threshold, 44.2% belong to the category 1 and the rest to the category 2. Similar, above the threshold, 60% of the data belongs to the category 1 and the rest to the category 2. 5.8

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Figure 5.8: Yearly salary with respect to the 'sex' column

The marriage column was converted into only two categories (1 and 2), because initially it contained more categories that were under represented (below 5% of the column data). The column 'race' contains imbalanced data, 78% of the data belonging to the category 1 and the rest to category 0. The 'age' column was converted into three categories: 'Less than 30', 'Between 30-50' and 'More than 50'. Since there is no information about the categories, the reference groups were the ones that had the highest representation per attribute. Looking at the FNR disparities in Figure 5.9 it can be observed that:

- The FNR is 2.5x higher for the age category 'Less than 30', although the distribution of the three categories is balanced.
- There is also a higher disparity for the 'marital status' category.
- The FNR disparity for 'race' is slightly unfair, the FNR rate for category 0 being only with 1.6x higher than the reference one. Also, the algorithm seems to prefer the 'sex' category 1, given the fact that the FNR rate for category 2 is 1.8x times higher.
- The attributes 'age', 'sex' and 'marital status' have asterisks next to their categories, which means that all three are significant attributes.

5.3 Income: yearly salary prediction dataset (2)

Figure 5.9: FNR disparities

Alternatively, the FOR parity is met for almost all groups. It can be seen in Figure 5.10 that besides for 'age' category, the FOR rates per attribute are similar.

5 Results and discussion

Figure 5.10: FOR rates

- **Conclusion:** Having a larger dataset with more entries does not necessarily imply that the bias is mitigated.

5.4 Education: law school admission dataset

- **Results and analysis:** In this dataset there are again imbalances for the sensitive attributes, specifically for the 'race' attribute where 85% of the entries belonged to the 'white' category and the rest to 'other' category. The gender attribute was more balanced: 56% men and 44% women. The split of the data was done as follows: train set, test set (20% of the data) and validation (25% of the data). For this task Random Forest algorithm performed the best. The following groups were defined as reference:
 - 'gender': Male.
 - 'age': 'More than 60'. The median value for the 'age' column was 61, therefore the column was transformed into two categories: 'Less than 60' and 'More than 60'.
 - 'race': White.

The Aequitas output showed disparities for the FDR and FNR. It can be noted from 5.11 and 5.12 that:

- For both 'age' and 'race' attributes, the FDR for the non-reference groups are high. A high FDR rate means that for instance for 'race'

5.4 Education: law school admission dataset

category 'other' the chances of having the algorithm predict that the exam was passed, even though it was not are higher than for the reference group.

- The FNR fails to meet parity for all three sensitive attributes, although for 'age' the disparity rate is very close to the upper limit of the fairness criteria (1.25). However, for 'race' the value is very large which is caused by the fact that for the 'white' category the FNR rate is close to 0 ($\approx 0,003$), while for the 'other' category is 0.07

Figure 5.11: FDR rates

Figure 5.12: FNR rates

- **Conclusion** Again, imbalances in the sensitive attributes affect the results of the predictions for the categories that are less represented in the dataset.

6 Conclusions

The aim of this project was to investigate whether and to what degree public datasets, which can be used for decision making across various domains, do contain bias. Such datasets can be used by machine learning models as training data in order to make decisions that can affect people's lives. Therefore it is one essential approach to address the bias problem and investigate whether it exists on a data level, before training machine learning algorithms on them. The here presented investigation was done using Aequitas, an audit toolkit that provides bias metrics that can indicate where unfairness can be found in a dataset, given a set of sensitive attributes. The toolkit was used to evaluate a set of selected datasets: and four of them from three different topics (education, health and income) were presented and discussed in this project. There was bias present in all four datasets and one of the main reasons was the fact that there was an imbalance either in the label distribution or in the collected samples.

This project was an evaluation of bias in datasets, therefore future work could include trying to mitigate bias using different approaches and then evaluate whether the fairness of the results is improved or not.

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